

Primary Nutrients Status of Three Vermicomposts Produced in a Nigerian Sahel Region

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Received: 3 Pqngo dgt 2023

Accepted: 12'Crtkn2024

Abstract

A pot experiment was conducted at the soil and water laboratory of Federal University Gashua Nigeria, to assess the reaction and primary nutrients – NPK, and Organic Carbon (OC) status of three white grub-produced Vermicompost using different ingredients (Municipal Waste – M_W , Typha Grass – T_P , and Municipal Waste + Typha Grass – $M_W T_0$). Laid on a Completely Randomized Design (CRD), the number of live worms, worms' weight, Vermicompost weight, and worms' mortality percentage as production indices were recorded and statistically analyzed upon Vermicompost maturity. Matured Vermicompost Reaction (pH and EC) and Primary nutrients (NPK), and OC were determined in another laboratory upon taking the respective compost samples as Soil health Indices. The result of the analysis showed that M_W has the highest Nitrogen (%) = 1.60, the highest available Phosphorus = 0.47 mgKg⁻¹, and the highest Exchangeable Potassium = 720 mgKg⁻¹, it also presented a mildly acidic reaction (pH=6.8), with the highest percentage of OC (2.80%) and the lowest basic salts EC = 0.35 dS/m. In terms of earlier determined live worm percentage, live worm weight, Vermicompost weight, and worm mortality rate, the highest findings are M_W = 64.5 %, M_W = 40 grams, M_W = 301 grams, and T_P = 66.9 % respectively. In conclusion, M_W Vermicompost proves to be the best, taking into consideration its better indices. As the premier of its kind in the study area, among other recommendations, we encourage setting this study as a pilot, and

the conduct of more studies on the efficiency of Vermicompost on soil health and crop production in the study area.

Keywords: vermicompost, vermicompost production, primary nutrients, sahel savannah, soil health

Introduction

Vermicomposting is the decomposition of organic residues in an aerobic environment by exploiting the optimum biological activity of earthworms and microorganisms (Garg and Gupta, 2009). Studies on the production of important vegetable crops like tomatoes (*Lycopersicon esculentum*), and eggplant (*Solanum melongena*) using Vermicompost have yielded very good results in Asia (Adhikary, 2012; Ashiwar & Hussain, 2015). Similarly, the overall productivity of many classes of crops was significantly boosted by Vermicompost applied at reasonable amounts per unit area (Adhikary, 2012). Positive findings after the use of Vermicompost as a source of organic manure in supplementing and/or substituting chemical fertilizers lead to it becoming popular among farmers around the world (Joshi *et al.*, 2015). Application of Vermicompost was reported in several literature to enhance most inherent biogeochemical aspects of crop production (Sinha *et al.*, 2009; Ashiwar & Hussain, 2015; Dhanalakshmi *et al.*, 2014; Joshi *et al.*, 2015), as well as its economy (Lim *et al.*, 2015). A Study also suggested that Vermicompost enhances the formation of humic acid and plant growth-promoting bacteria, which is a plus for soil health and sustainable agriculture especially in the tropics (Laufer and Tomlinson, 2013).

Vermicast, a cocoon compound produced during Vermicomposting, produced a higher percentage of the protein and carbohydrate contents as compared to chemical fertilizer in the study of Adhikary (2012). Vermicast was established to be the active constituent, and its action was believed to produce higher garden pea pods per plant, higher green grain weight per plant, and higher green pod yield per hectare as compared to chemical fertilizer, and the overall vegetable production (Adhikary, 2012; Ahirwar & Hussain, 2015).

Recently, Organic farming inputs have been adopted by farmers to boost soil fertility, OC content and the general health of arable soils (Lim *et al.*, 2015). However, the knowledge of deliberate Vermicomposting is among the limiting techniques in agricultural production to the farmers, especially in the Sahel Region of Nigeria. Also, evident is the fact that, chemically synthesized inorganic fertilizers pose economic, health, and degradative risks in the long run (Adugna & Abegaz, 2015).

Located in the Sahel Savannah Agro-ecological zone, in the northern parts of Yobe State of North Eastern Nigeria, Gashua is a predominantly farming and fishing community. Despite its unfavorable climatic condition and low annual rainfall (500 to 1000mm) (FDALR, 1990), Gashua soil is fertile and suitable for cultivation of cereal, tubers, fruits, and vegetable (Alhassan *et al.*, 2018). The soil, however, was reported to have low OC content, a crucial site for ion exchange and buffering (Sani *et al.*, 2019).

In the Nigerian Sahel, with inorganic fertilizers being costly, sometimes scarce, and elsewhere regarded as a security threat, subsistent farmers find it economically impossible to apply enough for good growth (Alhassan *et al.*, 2018). These Farmers depend largely on locally sourced organic fertilizers on one hand (Makinde *et al.*, 2010; Sani *et al.*, 2023). On

the other hand, a huge amount of waste in the form of Municipal Waste (M_W), Farm yard Manure (FYM), and numerous indigenous and exotic grasses that colonize farmlands and waterways such as Typha species, are generated and heaped on dump sites, posing potential environmental pollution and hazard (Agboola and Omueti, 1982). Incorporating these waste materials into the soil for crop production would serve as a source of organic farming inputs to build up an organic matter layer that is needed for a steady supply of nutrients in tropical soils (Agboola and Omueti, 1982; Noma and Sani, 2008), as well, a measure for pollution and bio-degradable waste control.

The potential of Vermicomposting to turn municipal, waterways, and on-farm waste materials into an important farming input makes it an attractive proposition. Vermicomposting offers benefits such as enhanced soil fertility and soil health that engender increased agricultural productivity, improved soil biodiversity, reduced ecological risks, and a better environment (Adhikary, 2012; Sinha et al., 2009; Ashiwar & Hussain, 2015; Barik et al., 2011; Dhanalakshmi et al., 2014; Dominquez & Edwards, 2004; Garg & Gupta, 2009; Joshi et al., 2015; Lim et al., 2015; Mistry, 2015; Sinha et al., 2010). However, many farmers, and especially those in developing countries and this study area, find themselves at a disadvantage as they fail to make the best use of organic recycling opportunities using earthworms. Thus, Vermicomposting could be one of the valuable options for Sahel region farmers to restore or enhance their agricultural soil's health.

The major objective of this study is to know the reaction, primary nutrient and OC status of three Vermicomposts produced with different raw materials. Specific aims of the study include: Producing Vermicompost and comparing the production indices of different Vermicomposts

Materials and methods

This research was carried out at Federal University Gashua (FUGA). Gashua is a community located on Latitude: $12^{\circ}52'26''$ N Longitude: $11^{\circ}02'26''$ E Elevation above sea level: 339 m = 1112 ft in Yobe State, northeastern Nigeria.

Experimental design

The experiment was laid out on a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) where three vermicomposts are produced using three different ingredients (Fiber) in three times replica containers. The main raw materials are that make the three Vermicompost treatments are:

1. Municipal Waste (M_W)
2. Dried Typha Grass (T_P)
3. 50% Municipal Waste + 50 % Dried Typha Grass ($M_W T_0$)

Vermicompost production

Organic waste in the forms; Farmacyard Manure (FYM), Municipal Refuse, and the White Grub worms were obtained from the Animal Science Teaching and Research Farm,

Faculty of Agriculture, Federal University, Gashua. Typha grass was obtained along Garbi River, a delta on the Hadejia-Nguru Wetlands, all in Yobe State, Nigeria.

During preparation for the compost production, all organic wastes were sorted and air dried for a week. 11 white grub worms were introduced to perforated pots each for the three compost ingredients mentioned in 3.3 above, upon which an equal weight of the raw materials and farm yard manures was added. 100ml of distilled water was then sprinkled on the mix and the containers were covered. The same procedure was replicated three times for each treatment. Typha grass was shredded to increase its surface area and increase decomposition during rate. This setup was monitored and turned daily for three weeks and data was taken on the 21st day after set up.

Sampling and determination of Vermicompost nutrient status

A sample was collected from each of the matured Vermicomposts and used to determine Electrical Conductivity (EC), pH, Total Nitrogen (N), Available Phosphorus (P), Exchangeable Potassium (K) and Organic Carbon (OC) using standard laboratory procedures at the soil science laboratory, Bayero University Kano.

EC and pH were determined with its respective meters using the method as described in (Mitchell and Soga, 2005). Total Nitrogen (N) was determined using the Kjeldhal digestion method in (Bouajila and Sanaa, 2011). Phosphorus (P) in Cmol/Kg was determined using Extractable Phosphate Bray and Kurtz –Method (Department of Sustainable Natural Resources, 1995), and converted to mg/Kg using the conversion factor 1cmol/Kg =10,000mg/Kg. Exchangeable Potassium (K) was determined using the Ammonium saturation method described by (Burt, 2014). Organic Carbon (OC) was determined using wet oxidation using the method of Walkley and Black (1934).

Method of data collection

Data on mortality rate, number of live worms, weight of worms and compost weight were collected and recorded from Sample containers at compost maturity.

White grub worms species Mortality rate:

The mortality rate of white grub worms which were placed in the different prepared Vermicompost medium for the experiment was recorded by turning the sample with a spatula and watching with eye visibility count at compost maturity.

Percentage of live White grub worms:

Live worms in the respective pots after compost maturity were counted and the percentage was determined from the initial number at the start of the experiment.

Weight of White grub worms:

The weights of the worms in 3.5.2 above were determined using a digital weighing balance.

Vermicompost weight:

Matured Vermicompost of all pots was weighed after the removal of live and dead worms using a weighing balance.

Data analysis

The Vermicompost production indices data recorded from all pots was subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using STAR 2.2 edition.

L.S.D was employed for mean separation where significance existed at 0.5% probability.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 and figure 1 above show the production indices of the three vermicomposts produced in this study. Vermicompost weight shows a statistically significant variation among the composts at maturity, M_W with 301g is higher in biomass and statistically different from T_P with 204 g which was also significantly different from $M_W T_0$ which weighs 249g. The percentage of live worms is highest in M_W as a substrate at 64.5, followed by 24.7% for $M_W T_P$. The $M_W T_P$ seemed to be the most favorable substrate to the worms, as the average live worm weighed 59.1g showcasing statistical supremacy over $M_W = 40g$, and $T_P = 20.8g$. In terms of worm mortality, however, the highest value indicates a worse substrate for the worm's survival and in that, single Typha T_P proved to be the worst. At the same time, $M_W T_0$ was the best attesting to the magnitude of the worms' average weight in grams.

Table 1. Vermicompost production indices

Vermicompost type	Vermicompost weight (g)	Live worms (%)	Earthworm weight (g)	Mortality rate %
M_W	301 ^a	64.5 ^a	40.0 ^b	30.0 ^b
T_P	204 ^c	5.5 ^c	20.8 ^c	66.9 ^a
$M_W T_0$	249 ^b	24.7 ^b	59.1 ^a	28.0 ^c
Mean	251.3	31.6	39.9	48.3
LSD	15.79	5.52	4.08	18.8

M_W = Municipal Waste Vermicompost; T_P = Typha Grass Vermicompost;

$M_W T_0$ = 50% Municipal Waste + 50 % Dried Typha Grass

Figure 1. Vermicomposts indices during production

Looking at the production indices, the two vermicomposts that contain municipal waste (M_w) performed better in this study. This could be probably due to its constitution of many species of biodegradable wastes sourced largely from table drops and household wastes, thereby supplying a variety of substrates for the worms to thrive. (Garg and Gupta, 2009; Lim et.al., 2015) mentioned a similar possibility as a reason for production and nutrient level disparity in agro-industrial waste. Also, Type grass as a substrate may be rich in Carbon and Hydrogen but less in peptides, which may diminish its performance as against M_w containing vermicompost (Ahirwar & Hussain, 2015)

Table 2. *Vermicomposts reaction, primary nutrients (NPK), and Organic Carbon status*

Parameter	M_w	T_p	M_wT_0
pH in H_2O	6.85	7.26	7.37
EC (dS/m)	0.35	0.36	1.10
Total Nitrogen –N (%)	1.95	0.80	0.80
Phosphorous – P ($mgKg^{-1}$)	0.47	0.35	0.37
Potassium –K ($mgkg^{-1}$)	0.72	0.49	0.4
Organic Carbon (%)	2.80	1.20	1.80

M_w = Municipal Waste Vermicompost; T_p = Typha Grass Vermicompost

M_wT_0 = 50% Municipal Waste + 50 % Dried Typha Grass

Figure 2. *Soil health Indices of the produced Vermicomposts*

Table 2 and figure 2 shows the reaction and primary nutrients (NPK) status of the vermicomposts produced in Table 1 above. Both T_p and M_wT_0 vermicomposts are neutral in terms of reactivity (pH), which attests to a good quality soil amendment and provides the

favorable conditions needed for plant and Rhizosphere conditions for good production. Percentage Organic Carbon (OC) in the vermicomposts produced is at least 1% higher in M_w than either of T_p and M_wT₀. 2.80%, 1.20%, and 1.80% was the respective percentages for M_w, T_p, and M_wT₀. The recorded variations in the selected soil health indices could be as a result of the nutritional constitution of the major ingredients of the vermicomposts as reported in (Barik et al., 2011). Also, the OC content of all the produced vermicomposts, is way above the average OC content of the soils of the study area reported in many literature (Alhassan et al., 2018; James & A, 2019; Sani et al., 2019; Wikipedia, 2020). This is an indicator of OC supplementing power of all Vermicompost produced (despite different levels) when and if incorporated to the soil.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the use of organic fertilizer especially Vermicompost has a great impact on improving the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the soil. Most importantly, Vermicomposting is the easiest way of conserving the soil and reducing environmental waste. Findings in this study establish the superiority of organic wastes from Municipal dump site. The product from such fibers and organic materials produced the best set of Vermicompost production indices and Vermicompost-soil health indicators.

Recommendation

Taking this research as a pilot, we recommend subsequent studies that will research the substrate type and rate, for a more informed compost recommendation and the undertaking of organic farming in the Sahel region.

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